

collapses to give triphenyl-phosphine oxide and thioxanthene-9-hydrazone (IV). The latter suffers further C = N bond cleavage to yield V and hydrazine hydrate. Such a behaviour recalls the formation of carbonyl compounds by hydrolysis of ketazines³.

When, on the other hand, the reaction of I with triphenyl-phosphine was carried out in boiling petroleum ether, both the phosphazine (II) and dithiodixanthylene (VI) were isolated. The latter ethylenic compound arises via partial decomposition of compound I upon heating⁴.

- VII
- a, R = H; R' = Cl
 - b, R = R' = Cl
 - c, R = H; R' = P(O)(OCH₃)₂
 - d, R = H; R' = P(O)(OC₂H₅)₂
 - e, R = H; R' = P(O)(OC₃H_{7-i})₂
 - f, R = H; R' = P(O)(OH)₂
 - g, R = R' = P(O)(OCH₃)₂
 - h, R = R' = P(O)(OC₂H₅)₂
 - i, R = R' = P(O)(OC₃H_{7-i})₂

With triisopropyl phosphite, compound I, in petroleum ether, gives dithiodixanthylene (VI) together with thioxanthene-9-hydrazone (IV). The formation of IV is believed to result from the decomposition of unstable 9-diazothioxanthene-triisopropyl phosphite adduct, though this has not been isolated,

As complement to previous work⁵ on the behaviour of 9-chloro-xanthene towards trialkyl phosphites, we have now investigated the same reaction on their sulphur analogues (e.g., VIIa and VIIb). Under the Michaelis-Arbuzov reaction conditions, 9-chlorothioxanthene (VIIa) reacts with trimethyl-, triethyl-, and/or triisopropyl phosphite to yield the corresponding 9-phosphonate derivatives (VIIc-e). The identity of these compounds was established by correct analytical results and by the fact that upon treatment with aqueous hydrochloric acid (15%), they give one and the same product (VIIf). The I.R. spectrum of VIIe, in chloroform, shows bands at 1580 cm^{-1} (aromatic band); 1310 cm^{-1} ($\equiv \text{P} = \text{O}$, non bonded)^{2c} and 1010 cm^{-1} ($\text{P}-\text{O}-\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$)^{2d}.

It seems probable that the reaction of VIIa and trialkyl phosphites proceeds via the formation of a complex between the formed carbonium ion and the tertiary phosphite ester^{5,6}. This mechanism finds analogy with that proposed by Smith and Burger⁷ and by Arbuzov and Arbuzov⁸ for secondary and tertiary halides, respectively.

Although the phosphonate derivatives VIIc-e are also formed under conditions unfavourable for free radical-formation, *vide infra*, the alternate mechanism, involving a homolytic path cannot be completely excluded, since bulky compounds, e.g., fluorenyl chloride can exist as relatively stable free radicals⁷.

9,9-Dichlorothioxanthene (VIIb) has been also found to undergo the Michaelis-Arbuzov reaction with trimethyl-, triethyl-, or triisopropyl phosphite to give the colourless tetraalkyl diphosphonates VIIg-i, respectively. This behaviour towards trialkyl phosphites simulates that of gem-dihalides, e.g., diiodomethane⁹ and of carbon tetrachloride¹⁰ towards these reagents. In the latter case, Kamai and Kharasova¹¹ proposed a radical-chain mechanism.

It is of interest to report here that 9,9-dichlorothioxanthene (VIIb) reacts with diphenylphosphinodithioic acid, a thiol phosphoric acid, to yield thioxanthene-9-thione (IX), almost quantitatively. This reaction establishes a new method for the formation of IX. The latter arises, presumably, via attack by the thiol on VIIb and subsequent elimination of

Scheme 2

hydrogen chloride from intermediate VIII, so formed (Scheme 2). In this sense, the effect of diphenylphosphinodithioic acid on VIIb simulates that of thioacetic acid¹².

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected. The petroleum ether and benzene used were dried over metallic sodium. Trialkyl phosphites were purified by treatment with sodium followed by fractional distillation,

The I.R. spectra were taken in a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer.

Action of triphenylphosphine on 9-diazothioxanthene (I) in petroleum ether. (a)-*On the cold* : Triphenylphosphine¹³ (0.52 g; 0.002 mole) was added to a suspension of freshly prepared 9-diazothioxanthene¹⁴ (0.45 g; 0.002 mole) in petroleum ether (40 ml; b.p. 60°–80°). The reaction mixture was taken in a tightly closed vessel for about 2 hrs, then kept at room temperature for 48 hrs. The precipitated material, so formed, was collected, washed with a small amount of cold benzene, then crystallised from cyclohexane to give the phosphazine (II) (0.9 g; 95%) as yellow needles, m.p. 153–155°.

Anal. Calc. for C₃₁H₂₃N₂PS : C, 76.52; H, 4.76; N, 5.76; P, 6.37; S, 6.71. Found : C, 76.30; H, 4.60; N, 5.85; P, 6.30; S, 6.92%.

(b) *On the hot* : A mixture of triphenylphosphine (0.52 g; 0.002 mole), 9-diazothioxanthene (0.67 g; 0.003 mole) and petroleum ether (40 ml; b.p. 60°–80°) was refluxed for 6 hrs on the steam bath. The substance that separated after cooling was collected and crystallized from cyclohexane to give yellow needles proved to be phosphazine (II) (m.p. and mixed m.p.) (yield ca. 0.3 g; 60%).

The petroleum ether filtrate after concentration and cooling to the room temperature, deposited a substance which after repeated crystallization from xylene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) yielded colourless crystals melted above 350° and proved to be dithiodioxanthylene¹⁴; yield ca. 30%.

Acid hydrolysis of compound II : A mixture of compound II (0.4 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1.18, 50 ml) was refluxed for 8 hrs. After cooling, the precipitated material was collected, washed with water and then crystallised from cyclohexane. The substance that deposited after cooling was filtered (0.13 g; 80%), crystallized from cyclohexane to give pale-yellow needles proved to be thioxanthene-9-one (V) [m.p. and mixed m.p. 210¹⁵].

The combined cyclohexane solutions were evaporated till dryness under reduced pressure and the residue that left was crystallized from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°) to give colourless crystals proved to be triphenylphosphine oxide¹⁶ (m.p. and mixed m.p.) (Yield 0.18 g; 85%).

Action of hydrochloric acid on thioxanthene-9-hydrazone (IV) : A mixture of compound IV¹⁷ (0.5 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1.18; 50 ml) was refluxed for 8 hrs. After cooling and addition of cold water, the precipitated material was collected, washed with water and crystallized from cyclohexane to give thioxanthene-9-one (V) (m.p. and mixed m.p.), in a 80% yield.

Action of triisopropyl phosphite on 9-diazothioxanthene (I) : Freshly distilled triisopropyl phosphite¹⁸ (0.34 g; 0.002 mole) was slowly added to a suspension of compound I (0.67 g; 0.003 mole) in petroleum ether (40 ml; b.p. 60°–80°) with shaking and the mixture left at room temperature for 48 hrs. The substance that separated was collected (0.2 g), crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) to give pale-yellow crystals proved to be thioxanthene-9-hydrazone (IV) (m.p. and mixed m.p. 115¹⁷).

The filtrate was concentrated to half its original volume and the deposited material collected (0.2 g), crystallized from xylene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°), m.p. above 350° and proved to be dithiodixanthylene (VI)¹⁴.

Reaction of 9-chlorothioxanthene (VIIa) with trimethyl phosphite : To a cooled solution of 9-chlorothioxanthene (VIIa)¹⁹ (0.46 g; 0.002 mole) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added a solution of trimethyl phosphite¹⁸ (0.37 g; 0.003 mole) in dry benzene (10 ml) and the mixture left at room temperature for 48 hrs. The volatile materials were distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue left was collected, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°), then crystallized from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) to give VIIc as colourless needles (75%), m.p. 185°–187°.

Anal. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₅O₃PS : C, 58.81; H, 4.93; P, 10.11; S, 10.46. Found : C, 58.72; H, 4.88; P, 10.39; S, 10.34%.

Similarly, compounds VIId and VIIe were obtained by the reaction of VIIa with triethyl-,¹⁸ and triisopropyl phosphite¹⁸, respectively.

Compound VIId was crystallized from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) as colourless crystals (70%), m.p. 115°–117°.

Anal. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₉O₃PS : C, 61.06; H, 5.73; P, 9.26; S, 9.59. Found : C, 61.12; H, 5.70; P, 9.17; S, 9.52%.

Compound VIIe was obtained as colourless crystals from *n*-hexane, m.p. 129°–131° (yield 75%).

Anal. Calc. for C₁₉H₂₃O₃PS : C, 62.96; H, 6.39; P, 8.55; S, 8.83. Found : C, 63.19; H, 6.18; P, 6.39; S, 8.76%.

Similar results were obtained upon reacting VIIa with the trialkyl phosphite(s) in the absence of solvent, at 100°.

Reaction of 9-chlorothioxanthene with triisopropyl phosphite in the presence of hydroquinone : To a cooled solution of 9-chlorothioxanthene (0.5 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) containing a few mgms of hydroquinone, was added a solution of triisopropyl phosphite¹⁸ (0.4 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) and the mixture left at room temperature for 48 hrs. After evaporating the volatile materials under reduced pressure, the residual material was collected, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°), crystallized from *n*-hexane and proved to be VIIe (m.p. and mixed m.p.) (yield 70%).

Action of hydrochloric acid on VIIc : A mixture of compound VIIc (0.4 g) and dilute aqueous hydrochloric acid (50 ml, 1 : 1) was boiled under reflux for 4 hrs. After cooling, water was added and the precipitated material collected, washed with water, then crystallized from ethanol-water mixture to give VIIf as colourless crystals (yield 70%), m.p. 248°–250°.

Anal. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₁O₃PS : C, 56.11; H, 3.98; P, 11.13; S, 11.52. Found : C, 56.16; H, 4.06; P, 11.35; S, 11.33%.

Compound VIIf was similarly obtained by the action of dilute aqueous hydrochloric acid on VIId and VIIe, respectively. It dissolves freely in dilute aqueous (10%) sodium hydroxide and gives a yellow colour reaction with concentrated sulphuric acid.

Reaction of 9,9-dichlorothioxanthene (VIIb) with trimethyl phosphite: To a cooled solution of 9,9-dichlorothioxanthene (VIIb)¹⁹ (0.53 g; 0.002 mole) in dry benzene (30 ml), was added a solution of trimethyl phosphite¹⁸ (0.37 g; 0.003 mole) in 5 ml benzene. The reaction mixture was refluxed on the steam bath for 3 hrs. After removal of benzene and volatile materials under reduced pressure, the remaining oily residue was washed for several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°), then crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) to give VIIg (75%) as colourless crystals, m.p. 167°–169°.

Anal. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{20}O_8P_2S$: C, 49.27; H, 4.86; P, 14.95; S, 7.74. Found: C, 49.34; H, 4.77; P, 14.60; S, 7.68%.

Similarly, compounds VIIh and VIIi were obtained by the action of triethyl-, and triisopropyl phosphite, respectively, on VIIb.

Compound VIIh was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) as colourless crystals (yield 70%), m.p. 145°–147°.

Anal. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{28}O_8P_2S$: C, 53.61; H, 5.99; P, 13.17; S, 6.82. Found: C, 53.56; H, 5.85; P, 13.20; S, 6.81%.

The colourless crystals of VIIi (75%) were obtained from benzene, m.p. 209°–211°.

Anal. Calc. for: $C_{25}H_{36}O_8P_2S$: C, 57.02; H, 6.89; P, 11.76; S, 6.08. Found: C, 57.32; H, 6.91; P, 11.66; S, 6.23%.

Reaction of 9,9-dichlorothioxanthene (VIIb) with diphenylphosphinodithioic acid: To a cooled solution of VIIb (0.53 g; 0.002 mole) in dry benzene (30 ml) was added diphenylphosphinodithioic acid²⁰ (0.5 g; 0.002 mole). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr (whereby hydrogen chloride gas ceased to evolve). The benzene solution was concentrated to half its original volume and petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) added. The substance that deposited after cooling was collected, crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) and proved to be thioxanthene-9-thione (IX) (m.p. and mixed m.p. 170)¹⁴.

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